

WAYS OF COOPERATION BETWEEN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS AND SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: In this article, the main task of all of us today, our human duty is to raise a perfect generation. That’s why all good deeds in our country should be done primarily to strengthen families and ensure a bright future for the young generation. After all, if the family is healthy, the society is strong, if the society is strong, the country is stable. Children’s upbringing is not only the responsibility of the family, educational institutions, but also the neighborhood. Because child education depends on many factors, first of all, the moral and spiritual environment. It was highlighted that family cooperation with educational institutions is important in this

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Fundamental political and economic reforms covering all spheres of society have been implemented in our country since the first steps towards independence. Great changes are being made in the field of education, including preschool education, which is considered its first step. Consistency between preschool educational institution and school is also reflected in the forms and methods of education. Today, this consistency is a matter of dosage. In cooperation with the neighborhood, the pre-school education organization will identify children who are not included in the preschool educational organization and involve them in short-term groups, distribute the book "Five Names" and "Seven Names" to families in

order to prepare children for school education in a quality way, and monitor the organization of the educational process in families with the participation of parents. leads to the improvement of the development of the sector. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev states that "modern preschool education plays an important role in raising a healthy and mature generation." Currently, special attention is paid to preparing children for high-quality school education in preschool educational organizations under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a proof of this, in 2018, the coverage of children in the field of preschool education was 34.4%, and this indicator was 40.5% at the end of the half-year of 2019. This is definitely the result of the decisions and attention of the head of state in the field of preschool education. A valid question arises here. How to turn the educational process from a difficult one into a joyful one? It is worth mentioning that quality education depends primarily on the professional skills of the educator and pedagogue.

In the years of independence, the country adopted the "Law on Education" and "National Personnel Training Program" regulating the activities of educational institutions. Great changes have taken place in the field of education, including preschool education, which is considered its first step. Article 30 of the "Law on Education" increased the role and responsibility of parents in the upbringing of children and their education, protection of their legal rights and interests. The transition of a preschool-age child to school education brought about serious radical changes in his life, morals, interests and relationships.

Therefore, it is necessary to prepare a preschool child for school education in a preschool educational organization or family, to familiarize him with knowledge, understanding, skills and abilities that are not difficult for him. Giving a good upbringing to a child in the family is the main goal and task facing the parents

from the very beginning of the child's life, that is, debt is obligatory for the parents as well.

Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3955 dated September 30, 2018 "On measures to improve the management of the preschool education system" and the decision of the Minister of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 21, 2018 - based on order No. 2-MX of November, the supervisory board started working in preschool education organizations.

Comprehensive cooperation between kindergarten and school is the main condition for successful implementation of the task of preparing children for school education.

The connection between the kindergarten and the school requires, on the one hand, to transfer children to school with general development and upbringing to meet the requirements of school education, and on the other hand, the teacher relies on the knowledge, skills and experiences of children of senior kindergarten age and uses them in the educational process. enough. The organic connection between the kindergarten and the school helps bring the conditions of education closer to the children of the senior kindergarten age and the students of the primary class of the school.

Employees of pre-school education institutions should be familiar with the requirements for children in the first grade, and prepare children in the preparatory group for school accordingly. The organic relationship between school and kindergarten has a complex and multifaceted structure. In it, it is possible to distinguish the leading aspects of educational work, such as the content, methods and methods, organizational forms, as well as the conditions of raising children and pedagogical requirements.

It is necessary to pay attention to the following: - from the point of view of school requirements, children should acquire knowledge more deeply; - from the

point of view of kindergarten, it is necessary to equip children with knowledge, skills, and abilities at the level of school requirements; - mental readiness of children for school.

Preschool education is the initial stage of the continuous education system and is organized based on the requirements of the Law "On Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Pre-school education creates the necessary organizational, methodological, psychological, and pedagogical conditions for raising healthy, mature children in all respects, preparing children for regular education at school helps parents. In recent years, special attention has been paid to improving the system of preschool education, updating the form, tools and methods of educational content. Children's knowledge, skills and abilities are checked at the end of each academic year through control exercises. The level of school readiness of children aged 6-7 is checked based on the indicators of these state requirements.

Preparing the children of the Preparatory Group to study at school occupies an important place. It completes pre-school childhood and is considered a teacher's stage for schooling. At the same time, children's behavior and activities, which are important for further education related to their intellectual, spiritual-volitional and emotional spheres, are actively formed. The main attention of the educator of the preparatory group is focused on the full mastery of the content of the preschool education program for all children, as this is a mandatory condition for full preparation for school education. Pedagogical process in large groups, arising from the task of preparing children for school, is unique. This uniqueness is not only copying the educational work of the school, but also the special organization of children's activities and behavior aimed at forming the qualities necessary for successful teaching in school. When he comes to the preparatory group, the child begins to show himself independently in various activities: in self-service, on duty, in work in the heart of nature. The child's independence and organizational skills are formed under the direct guidance of the educator in all their activities. In

addition to the implementation of general tasks, the implementation of the physical education program instills in children the desire to willingly perform morning physical education and physical training, to improve their actions. Therefore, it is necessary to develop physical and mental activity of the child and the activity of movement that increases working ability. Preparing the children of the preparatory group for studying at school occupies an important place. It completes pre-school childhood and is the transition stage to school. At the same time, children's behavior and activities, which are important for further education related to their mental, spiritual-volitional and spiritual spheres, are actively formed. The main attention of the educator of the preparatory group is focused on the full mastery of the content of the preschool education program for all children, because this is a mandatory condition for full preparation for school education. Pedagogical process in large groups arising from the task of preparing children for school is unique. This uniqueness is not only copying the educational work of the school, but also the special organization of children's activities and behaviors aimed at forming the qualities necessary for successful teaching at school.

In conclusion, it should be noted that if the preschool educational organization, school, neighborhood, and family cooperation in preparing a child for school education is properly implemented, the quality and effectiveness of education and the goal set before us will be achieved. is important in implementation. The task of morally educating children of preschool age and the means of implementation are the formation of moral consciousness, feelings and behavior, which are important spiritual qualities of a person, love for the country, humanitarianism, attitude to work, attitude to joint research, conscious discipline and other the development of feelings is an important task of moral education. The task and content of morally educating preschool children in cooperation requires the education and development of the child's spiritual world, his mind, moral feelings, personal qualities and behavior.

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